

Daily Communal Petitions (Tefillah/Amidah)

Expert source: Ruth Langer, Boston College

Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

Entered by Brandon Brown, Baylor University

** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Early Rabbinism, Semitic, Late Second Temple Judaism, Religious Group, Prayer, Text, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, West Semitic, Language, Modern Hebrew, Canaanite, Northwest Semitic, Ritual text, Afro-Asiatic, Jewish Traditions, Central Semitic

The Tefillah ("the Prayer") or Amidah ("standing [prayer]") is a communal prayer of rabbinic Judaism, established by the Mishnah for each service, morning, afternoon, and evening (and an additional service on festive days). It consists of praise, petition, and thanksgiving to God. With a quorum, the prayer is recited by each individual participant and then repeated by a designated prayer leader (except in the evening). The Tefillah is divided into three sections – praise of the divine upon entering into God's presence (3 paragraphs); on weekdays, petitions for particular human needs (12/13 paragraphs), replaced by a single non-petitionary paragraph about the day on Sabbaths and holy days; and thanksgiving when concluding interaction with the divine (3 paragraphs) – with each paragraph of the prayer ending with "blessed are you, O LORD" followed by a name of God or a divine role. While the weekday Tefillah consists of 18 paragraphs in the version from the Land of Israel in late antiquity, the Babylonian tradition lengthens it to 19. Thematic expansions are also made to the service on occasions such as minor festivals, fast days, or the New Year. The language of the Tefillah was heavily influenced by the Bible. Its thematic structure and some language were fixed by the third and fourth centuries CE – with variations increasingly less tolerated over the centuries. There is evidence that the Tefillah/Amidah was being used in rabbinic circles as early as the late first century, but transmission was oral. Full prayer books emerge only in the late 9th c. (Seder Rav Amram Gaon); better manuscripts exist for the Siddur Rav Saadia Gaon (c. 925).

Date Range: 50 CE - 1000 CE

Region: The Land of Israel and Babylonia

Region tags: Western Asia, Asia, Iraq, Israel

The Land of Israel here covers from Beer Sheva to the Mediterranean coast, north to southern Lebanon, and east to at least the Golan Heights and the east bank of the Jordan. Babylonia refers to the entire Tigris and Euphrates area including Baghdad.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Langer, Ruth. "Daily Communal Petitions (Tefillah/Amidah)." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*,

edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 50 CE - 200 CE

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en>

Notes: Langer, Ruth. "Daily Communal Petitions (Tefillah/Amidah)." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 50 CE - 200 CE

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Oral -- written texts emerged only at the very end of this period!

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 50 CE - 200 CE

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The earliest known full manuscripts date to c. 1000. They are written on leather, parchment, papyrus, and paper (mostly). But most were not written at all but oral!

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Specify type of paper

– Specify: n/a

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Texts were primarily transmitted orally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Texts were transmitted orally, with the related flexibility in their precise language.

Notes: Elements of the text are referenced in rabbinic texts. Variations of the text were present depending on the geographical and cultural context, particularly as influenced by the cultural centers in the Land of Israel and Babylonia. If or how the text was used elsewhere until the end of this period is unknown.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: Text is primarily oral

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

— No

Notes: The Tefillah/Amidah is not official religious scripture, but was used as an official liturgical prayer for daily use in rabbinic circles and, later Jewish communities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the prayer is Hebrew, even in contexts where that was not the spoken language. It was transmitted as an oral text, not normally written down.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: Much of the language of the prayer derives from the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: Liturgical Hebrew emerges as a distinct form of Hebrew, blending biblical and rabbinic vocabulary and forms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Notes: Prayers in this period are primarily oral. When written texts emerge, they are consistent with other texts of their period in production values.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Notes: Hebrew's sacredness as a language derives from its being the language of revelation and the Bible in rabbinic understanding

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Notes: Judaism does not make a firm distinction between religious and non-religious institutions in this period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: Non-religious is an anachronistic category here. Once Aramaic and Arabic are written in Hebrew characters (technically, Aramaic characters...), they achieve a degree of sanctity too.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ideally, the prayer is recited daily by all Jews, whether or not they attend communal prayer. What happened and happens in reality is unknowable. Public prayer requires a minimum community of ten adult men.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is debate about this in the early end of the date range. Under Christian and Muslim rule, it became dangerous for Jews to proselytize and for members of the religious majority to convert to Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Karaism emerges in the end of this period as a rejection of rabbinic Judaism. Rabbinic Judaism itself might be understood as a reformist movement in its origins.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judeans in Babylonia and Judah

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: If this means, is it chanted? Yes, probably.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it read?

– No

Notes: The text was recited orally, sometimes recomposed in the process.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: According to the Mishnah, the Tefillah (later known as the Amidah) should be recited three times every weekday plus an additional time on Sabbaths and holy days. All but the evening prayer are also repeated by the presider in communal services.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Varies depending on congregation size. Minimum of ten adult men.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The prayer can be recited privately/individually as well.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ten adult men is the minimum for public prayer, but private recitation by individuals is also expected.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The Tefillah/Amidah is recited three times daily on weekdays, with an additional recitation added on Sabbaths and holy days. A fifth recitation is added on Yom Kippur.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– I don't know

Notes: Unclear what this category might mean. When individuals recite the prayer, they do so privately and in parallel.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: Distinct versions of the Tefillah existed in the Land of Israel and Babylonia, but were viewed as proper within each community. The variations between these were stylistic (though returning roughly the same structure) and containing varying theological references. Even within these two larger communities' versions of the Tefillah, individual communities likely developed slight changes to the Tefillah. In addition, though the prayer itself always included praises, petitions, and thanksgivings to the God, the petitions themselves were subject to change depending on the need of

the petitioners.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Age of extant version of text?

— Yes

Notes: The earliest preserved manuscripts date from c. 1000. Until late in the period, the prayer themselves were almost exclusively orally transmitted. There are discussions about the text dating back to the late first century, albeit only occasionally about specific wording. In general, specific wording remained flexible, especially in the Land of Israel.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Content of text?

— I don't know

Notes: Unclear what this category means. Yes, the text has content.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

— Yes

Notes: The performance of the text serves a covenant-maintaining function in offering formal worship of God as did the daily perpetual offerings in the Jerusalem Temple when that existed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

— No

Notes: Different versions were considered proper in different communities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the rabbinic prayer tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: Very gradually, with the process extending well into the High Middle Ages and still tolerating small differences.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Heads of rabbinic academies asserted their customs are the proper ones, especially towards the end of this period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Claims of authority could be and were rejected. Liturgical poetry generated variety that, in the Land of Israel, substituted for fixed texts and in Babylonia was added to them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to

the larger canon?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Notes: Not in this period. But the Tefillah/Amidah is just one element of the rabbinic prayer service.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the rabbinic prayer tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– I don't know

Notes: Unclear what this means or might point to. Judaism in this period does not distinguish between cultural and religious.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above. It is mostly not a written text in this period. Instructions are embedded in the Mishnah and the Talmuds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not refer to any authors. The oral text may have emerged significantly organically, so there is no authoritative "lineage" to its various versions, although scholars do try to reconstruct its emergence from the known later versions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The Seder Rav Amram Gaon and the Siddur Rav Saadia Gaon summarize the talmudic discussions about the various elements of the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text express authority of ethical guidelines? (E.g.: adat literature that dictates or records "customary practices")

– No

Notes: The Seder Rav Amram Gaon and the Siddur Rav Saadia Gaon summarize the

talmudic halakhic (legal) guidelines and customary practices. Ethics, per se, is not their concern.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there non-institutionalized "acceptable" social punishments specified?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there non-institutionalized "acceptable" social rewards specified?

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, a divine reward for conforming with rabbinic directives is posited, generally in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The text does not formulate a calendar, but it does operate according to the Jewish calendar. This is not a specifically religious calendar, but is that of Jewish life in general.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is, however, present in other rabbinic prayers of the same era.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judeans in Babylonia and Judah

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: The Jewish people in its entirety (not just elites) are in covenant with their God. This prayer itself is a human participation in this covenant. God's roles include protection, blessing, and overall favor, which are referenced several times within the Tefillah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: powerful, holy, forgiving, saving/redeeming

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Can reward

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Can punish

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Indirect causal efficacy in the world

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Exhibits positive emotion

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 50 CE - 200 CE

Region: Judeans in Babylonia and Judah

Status of Readership:

Exhibits negative emotion

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Only in very limited ways. Rabbinic Judaism understands prophecy to have

ended. New divine communication is not a source of authority. But interpretation of texts, especially the Bible, is a source of knowledge provided by God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life

— Yes

Notes: Not a source of authority in this period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams

— Yes

Notes: Not a source of authority in this period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices

— No

Notes: Prohibited biblically.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer and study of Torah traditions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: Study of Torah and prayer are required.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judeans in Babylonia and Judah

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Prayers reference the angelic liturgy. They are not "present" in praying community, but the

community itself participates in the angelic praise of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia
Status of Readership:

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia
Status of Readership:

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia
Status of Readership:

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia
Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia
Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia
Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Rabbinic teaching suggests that when ten men gather for prayer, God's indwelling spirit joins them. The Tefillah/Amidah thus is recited in the direct presence of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: God is never visible in rabbinic Jewish understanding.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Food

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

Notes: Scripture texts and other holy texts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Notes: The angels care about God. But importantly, only God is an appropriate object of human worship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: peace

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite people, general populace)

✓ Religious Specialists

✓ Non-elite (common

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite people, general populace)

✓ Religious Specialists

✓ Non-elite (common

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite people, general populace)

✓ Religious Specialists

✓ Non-elite (common

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite people, general populace)

✓ Religious Specialists

✓ Non-elite (common

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite people, general populace)

✓ Religious Specialists

✓ Non-elite (common

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite people, general populace)

✓ Religious Specialists

✓ Non-elite (common

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: peace and prosperity, ingathering of exiles, resurrection of the dead, rebuilding Jerusalem Temple

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: The hope is not given a date, so it could be in this lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: Hopefully, yes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: World's end is not the concern or expectation of the messiah. In general, proper human behavior is considered a factor in hastening the messiah's advent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Divine judgment event

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not in this prayer, nor universally expected. But this concept does exist.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

Notes: Better: re-establishment of the proper political system.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: Unclear. Perhaps the wicked will not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: righteousness -- but not part of this prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cooperation

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Notes: not explicitly

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Only on designated fast days by those who are able to fast.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require taboos on desired foods, but the Jewish Torah, which is referenced within the text, does.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

populace)

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The performance of the Tefillah/Amidah prayer is time-intensive and is expected to be done multiple times a day.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 4

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Depends on the size of the congregation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 8

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: For the person leading public prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: For the person leading public prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: unclear what this means.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: It remembers sacrifices that can no longer be offered on Sabbaths and holy days. Biblical texts commanding them are recited.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A segment of the community defined by its having acquired knowledge (of Torah)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Rabbis, defined by their acquisition of knowledge of Torah. Reproduction of the text is shaped by its fundamentally oral character for almost all of this period, and for most participants, for much longer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: Not from within the Jewish community. But there is evidence of Roman and Christian attempts to suppress it or part of it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Divine involvement in health and welfare.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: Not relevant to this era.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Not according to the text's language, but yes, in its context historically.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Historically, in the inserts for the holidays of Purim and Hanukkah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: The exile of Jews from the Land of Israel and the loss of self-government and the Temple were the result of Judea's subjugation to Rome and revolt against it. The Tefillah/Amidah prays for the reversal of this situation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: Petition for adequate agricultural yield (and rain to enable that).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Judea and Babylonia

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Pastoralism

Notes: all of the above except cannibalism (won't allow multiple selection...)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Land of Israel and Babylonia

Status of Readership:

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